

Research

Effect of Input-mix and Skill-mix on Cost and Outcome of Health Services: A Study of Selected Hospitals in Bangladesh

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Abstract: This study attempted to identify the influences of skill-mix and input-mix on patients' cost and outcome of health care services measured by EuroQol-5D. The data were collected from the District Hospitals (DHs) of Natore and Rajbari; and Upazila Health Complexes (UHCs) of Goalanda and Baliakandi in 2019. The Natore DH and Goalanda UHC are referred to as 'treatment facility' since they had better skill-mix and input-mix and the other two are referred to as 'comparison facility'. A total of 120 patients and/or attendants (thirty from each facility) from the Department of Medicine and Department of Surgery were interviewed and key informant interviews were conducted with the health managers of the facilities. It was evident that Natore DH had 13% more medical professionals and 10% other support staff than Rajbari DH; Goalanda UHC had 20% more medical professionals and 5% more support staff compared to Baliakandi UHC. On the other hand, considering functional equipment, Natore DH had 25% more than Rajbari DH and Goalanda UHC had 22% more compared to Baliakandi UHC. A significant difference was found between the treatment and comparison facilities for average total cost of the respondents (USD 52.26 vs USD 67.12, $p=0.016$) as well as for direct medical cost (USD 13.39 vs USD 27.80, $p=0.001$). The study also found a significant difference in the average score of EuroQol-5D ($p=0.000$) of the facilities (0.49 vs 0.15). Regression result showed that the availability of skill-mix and input-mix in the hospital resulted in a significant ($p=0.000$) rise in the score of EuroQol-5D of the patients by 0.27 and a significant ($p=0.016$) reduction of direct medical cost by USD 12.72. Key informant interviews with health managers also confirmed these quantitative findings. Based on both the qualitative and quantitative findings, the study proposed some recommendations for addressing the problems of skill-mix and input-mix.

Keywords: skill-mix, input-mix, EuroQol-5D, direct medical cost, indirect cost

1. Introduction

The capacity to provide standard, efficient and patient-centered services relies upon a health workforce of appropriate, well-motivated and properly skilled persons working in optimum environments (WHO, 2000). Determining and achieving the ‘right’ mixture of health personnel was found as one of the major challenge for many health care organizations and health systems in the World Health Report 2000 (WHO, 2000). Health care is labor-intensive and therefore the appropriate mixture of staff may be achieved with considering local priorities, given the available resources (Buchan & Poz, 2002). ‘Skill-mix’ usually refers to as the combinations of actions or skills required for performing each activity within the institution whereas ‘input-mix’ refers to the mix of required inputs (e.g., human resources, physical capital, and consumables) to produce the output (Buchan & Poz, 2002). Comparing with international standards, Bangladesh faces a critical shortage of skilled health workforces, in both an absolute and relative sense, where the distribution is biased towards urban areas (MOHFW, 2016; MOHFW, 2015; Banik, et al., 2017; World Bank, 2019). Besides, Bangladesh has a skewed distribution of the health workforce towards doctors with a ratio of 1:0.4:0.24 of doctors to nurses to technologists, whereas the ratio recommended by WHO is 1:3:5 (Bangladesh Health System Review, 2015). Greater understanding of service user preferences for various kinds of staffing (type, roles, numbers, etc.) is required to consider the cost and consequences relevant to them. Also, Bangladesh lacks proper input-mix within the government facilities (MOHFW, 2016). World Health Report (2010) stated about the supply shortage of equipment in government hospitals of Bangladesh (WHO, 2010).

There are enormous range of developed methods and initiatives for optimizing the performance of accessible workforce and achieving the proper number and blend of personnel required to produce high-quality care. Despite this, developing countries like Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan face many challenges in implementing human resource management practices in health sector (Naz, et al., 2012). In Bangladesh, although greater efforts are directed towards the expansion of healthcare services delivery, little attention is paid to the role of human resource management. . Lack of attention to human resource crisis acts as a key factor between the success and failure of health care services delivery in Bangladesh (Banik, et al., 2017). Ahmed, Hossain, Chowdhury, & Bhuiya (2011) mentioned about the severe crisis of health workforce in Bangladesh. As of 2007, there have been only around five physicians and two nurses per 10,000 population, indicating the ratio of nurse to the physician of only 0.4, with

particular shortages in hard-to-reach areas (Ahmed, Hossain, Chowdhury, & Bhuiya, 2011). The right use of human resources, right methods of selection of training, distribution of roles and responsibilities, incentives for better works, opportunities for promotion and professional advancement, effective design of the 'health team' with proper inputs may turn into more efficient and effective health care service delivery. This study attempted to search out the effect of skill-mix and input-mix on outcome and cost of care from the patients' perspective.

2. Related Literature

Dixon, Kaambwa, Nancarrow, Martin, & Bryan (2010) in England examined the association between skill-mix, patient outcome, length of stay and service cost in older peoples' intermediate care services and found that improved skill-mix in a hospital resulted in greater cost-saving, i.e. with one additional hospital staff of any type resulted in a 17% reduction in service cost ($p=0.011$). There was a weak evidence ($p=0.090$) that a higher ratio of support staff to qualified staff results in greater improvements in EQ-5D scores of patients. Thungjaroenkul, Cummings, & Embleton (2007) also found significant reductions in cost and length of stay with higher ratios of nursing personnel in hospital settings. Studies conducted by Kim, Han, Lee, Kwon, & Park, (2016) and Bourgeault, Kuhlmann, E., & Wrede (2008) also demonstrated similar results. Bourgeault, Kuhlmann, & Wrede (2008) suggested that skill-mix is often a possible solution to shortages of certain provider groups and their mal-distribution, rising health care cost and therefore the related desire to enhance the cost-effectiveness of health care service delivery and quality improvement, including professional development and quality of work-life concerns.

Anderson, Wiener, & Khatutsky (2006) showed that patient satisfaction is positively related to well-trained workers and respectful staff. They mentioned that consumer dissatisfaction resulted from an interruption in services than not having the similar worker overtime. Efforts to improve workforce issues are needed to enhance the quality of care of these services. Aiken et al. (2017), through a cross-sectional study, showed that richer nurse skill-mix resulted in lower odds of mortality ($OR=0.89$), lower odds of low hospital ratings from patients ($OR=0.90$) and lower odds of reports of poor quality ($OR=0.89$), poor safety grades ($OR=0.85$) and other poor outcome ($0.80 < OR < 0.93$) after adjusting for patient and hospital factors.

Task shifting, defined as delegating tasks to existing or new cadres with either less training or narrowly tailored training, has been suggested as a potential strategy to handle these challenges

(Fulton, et al., 2011). They showed that task shifting is a very important policy choice to help alleviate workforce shortages and skill-mix imbalances.

In Bangladesh, the involvement of the health workforce with the private sector has increased over the years, as revealed by an estimated 62% of the medical doctors working in the private sector in 2013 (Bangladesh Health System Review, 2015). From a service delivery perspective in public sector, the country faces particularly critical challenges in its health workforce. Of all sanctioned public posts for doctors, 27 percent remain unfilled; more widely, 20 percent of the posts are vacant and a few are vacant for years (DGHS, 2012). The vacancy includes 21% of posts for medical technologists, 9% for mid-level staff, and 13.4% in nursing services. The hard-to-reach areas have far worse vacancy rates than the above national figures. Skill-Mix imbalance is also a concerning issue, because the nurse-to-doctor ratio in Bangladesh is one nurse for more than two doctors in practice, the reverse of the ratio recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO), i.e., three nurses for one physician (Ahmed, Hossain, Chowdhury, & Bhuiya, 2011). In 2011, doctors made up 70% of the total registered professional workforce; the remaining 30 percent were support staff (MOHFW, 2012).

Although the number of training institutions are likely to increase, absolute shortages of medical professionals will continue in the coming years. Shortages stem from low public sector salaries (the entry-level salary is insufficient for a family of five, the average family size of Bangladesh), inadequate HRH production, combined with migration, inordinately slow recruitment, and difficulty in staff retention, particularly in remote areas (Ahmed, Hossain, Chowdhury, & Bhuiya, 2011).

The available literature on skill-mix and input-mix and their effects on the standard of care are mainly based on developed countries. There exists a gap for greater understanding of the current scenario of skill-mix and input-mix; and their effect on the cost incurred by the patients and the quality of care provided in our country perspective. This warranted for a study in our country and this study attempted to search out the effect of skill-mix and input-mix on the cost and outcome of healthcare.

3. Conceptual framework

Skill-mix in health care service provision is usually defined by having the number of staff, mixing the qualifications among them, a combination of junior-senior staff and a multidisciplinary mix. Inputs of a health care facility were divided into two segments: Health care input and Non-health care input. Health care inputs consist of the number of service providers, equipment and supplies, information system and pharmaceuticals.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for the effects of input-mix and skill-mix on cost and outcome in health services

Non-health care inputs comprise of transportation toward the facility and patient education. To capture the health status of the patients, the EQ-5D, formerly called the EuroQol, a generic measure was used. It used one question to assess each of 5 health domains: mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression and classification system ranges between 1 indicating full health through and -0.59 indicating extreme problems in the respective domain. The Quantitative data on patients' cost were derived from the interviews of patients or attendants or both. The study is directed to investigate the skill-mix and input factors in health care facilities affecting patients' cost including both direct and indirect cost and outcome of the services.

4. Operational definitions

Skill-mix

The term 'skill-mix' is often referred to the combination of posts within the establishment, the combination of employees in a post, the mix of skills available at a particular time, or it may denote the combinations of activities that comprise each role, instead of the mix of various job titles. Skill-mix involves changes i.e. increasing the number of personnel, using higher ratios of qualified and including higher ratios of senior staff members (Buchan & Poz, 2002).

Input-mix

The basic inputs for health service delivery include the human resources, physical capital, and medical and surgical requisites. The outputs are personal and non-personal health services. Inputs have direct implications on the cost of production. Some inputs are easily varied, like drugs, other medical supplies, and health care personnel, while other sorts of inputs, like structures and expensive equipment, are fixed in the short-run and cannot be varied. All inputs are variable in the long-run (WHO, 2000).

Cost of treatment

Total cost of treatment is often decomposed into direct medical cost and indirect cost. Patients must bear the direct cost (e.g., include hospital charges, medicine cost, diagnostic tests) that are associated with the treatment process directly for getting health care. There are also some other cost that are not directly associated with the treatment process but still patients and their relatives have to bear them (e.g., patient's/attendant's additional food/accommodation cost, travel cost, informal tips as well as opportunity cost of patient and attendant(s)) which are termed as indirect cost (Hardee, Platt, & Kasper, 2005).

Direct medical cost

There are cost such as physician/medical providers' charge, basic facility charge, diagnostic and laboratory charge, cost of equipment and instruments for health care which are termed as the direct cost of treatment.

Indirect cost

Indirect cost includes direct non-medical cost and productivity loss. Direct non-medical cost has some components which are defined below.

A. Direct non-medical cost

The food provided by the hospital authority is given less attention, resulting in inferior quality food, and even health risks for patients, some patients either bring food from home or buy additional food for them from outside of the hospital (Fernando & Wijesinghe, 2017). The cost they have to bear for buying food are termed as “patient’s additional food cost”.

As hospital authority does not provide food for the attendant(s), they have to bring food from home or buy from outside of the hospital. The cost borne in buying food for attendant(s) in this regard are termed as “attendants’ food cost”.

B. Productivity losses

Due to illness and admission in the hospital, patients must remain absent from job, in case of those who are employed, as well as their attendants. Those who are not employed but self-employed and/or engaged in their own business may lose income as they cannot be present at their respective work. Those who are day laborers cannot go out for daily work and forgo their income. In these cases, daily wage/profit or monthly wage/profit of patient and attendant(s) was obtained during the study period. Then they are used to calculate the productivity losses from the job.

For the housewives, there was no unique method of calculation for productivity losses. Efroymson, Biswas, & Ruma (2007), using a sample size of 630 married individuals across ten areas of Bangladesh, estimated the economic value of women’s contribution to household activities (Efroymson, Biswas, & Ruma, 2007). They found that the typical workday for a full-time housewife was 16 hours and estimated the unpaid household activities of females were worth USD 2.51/day and USD 11.92/day for rural and urban women, respectively¹. This valuation is the best available valuation regarding calculating productivity loss of housewives and was employed in this study for calculating patient and attendant(s) productivity loss who are housewives.

Outcome measures

To assess the health status of the patients, the EQ-5D, formerly called the EuroQol, a generic measure was used. EuroQol-5D evaluates health status in a standardized way, which was developed by the EuroQol Group to provide a simple, easy, and generic measure of health for clinical and economic appraisal (Devlin & Brooks, 2017). The EQ-5D measures the present

¹ 1 USD= BDT 85

physical condition of the patients which shed light on the standard of hospital provided care. (Devlin & Brooks, 2017). The EQ-5D-3L descriptive system comprises the subsequent 5 dimensions: mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort, and anxiety/depression. Each dimension has 3 levels: no problems, some problems, and extreme problems (Drummond, Sculpher, Torrance, & O'Brien, 1997). The respondent is asked to point his/her health state by ticking (or placing a cross) within the box against the most appropriate statement in each of the 5 dimensions in the TTO (Time Trade-off) method. The closer the score of EuroQol-5D to 1 the higher the standard of provided care (Drummond, Sculpher, Torrance, & O'Brien, 1997).

5. Methods

Design and study setting

A cross-sectional survey was conducted in 2019 with the inpatients at the Department of Medicine and also the Department of Surgery in Natore District Hospital, Rajbari District Hospital and two Upazila Health Complexes (UHCs) named Goalanda Upazila Health Complex and Baliakandi Upazila Health Complex. Both of the district hospitals are of 100 beds and the UHCs are of 50 beds during the study period. Natore is a district of Rajshahi Division, located in northern Bangladesh. There are eight pourasavas (municipality) and seven upazilas in Natore district. The total population is 17,06,673; among them male are 8, 54,183 and female are 8, 52,490. Most part of Natore district is plain land and its economy is based on agriculture. Natore District Hospital ranked 11th among the 62 hospitals in the DGHS Hospital Ranking of Government Hospitals of Bangladesh published by DGHS (MOHFW, 2015). On the other hand, Rajbari is a district in central Bangladesh. It is a part of the Dhaka Division. There are three pourasavas and five upazilas in Natore district. The total population is 10,15,519; among them, male are 5, 24,624 and female are 4, 90,895. Most part of Rajbari district are based on alluvial soil of Padma River and it is a flood-prone area. Economy of Rajbari is based on agriculture. There are 1 district hospital, 3 Upazila Health Complexes, 28 Union Sub-Centers and 24 Family Welfare Centers in Rajbari. These study areas were selected based on the convenient sampling considering the accessibility and affordability of the researcher to conduct a quantitative survey. The study considered Natore district hospital and Goalanda UHC as 'treatment facilities' as these two facilities possess a better skill-mix and input-mix compared to the other two 'comparison facilities', i.e., Rajbari DH and Baliakandi UHC. These hospitals are considered treatment facilities or comparison facilities based upon the readiness of input of the equipment and also the skill of the service providers.

A sample of inpatients of selected general male and female wards of the above mentioned departments from the four hospitals were interviewed to collect quantitative and qualitative data. Key Informant Interviews (KII) were conducted with the superintendent of two district hospitals (DHs), Upazila Health and Family Planning Officer (UHFPO) and Residential Medical Officer (RMO) from two Upazila Health Complexes (UHCs); documents related to human resources and equipment of the hospital were reviewed for assessing the skill-mix and input-mix. Cost of treatment and outcome were collected from either the patient or his/her close relative who were staying with the patient as attendant(s) through a face to face interview.

Study population

The study surveyed 120 patients from the inpatient wards of the Department of Medicine and the Department of Surgery in the above-mentioned healthcare facilities. Thirty patients from each of the facilities were interviewed, thus there were 60 respondents from the treatment facilities and 60 from the comparison facilities. The survey respondents were conveniently selected; patients with odd bed numbers were included in the survey and patient who were not in a state to be surveyed (severely ill, elderly, debilitated patient), physically or mentally challenged (deaf and mute) were not included. Key informant interviews (KIIs) were conducted with at least one health manager (e.g., superintendent, UHFPO, RMO, etc.), purposively selected from each of the facilities.

Selection of variables and indicators

Data on five broad groups of variables categories: socio-demographic characteristics, the usual practice for seeking health care services, information on current/present disease, cost related to treatment, and information related to measuring EuroQol-5D were collected during the survey. The survey comprehensively included socio-demographic characteristics (e.g., age, education, occupation, household income, marital status, etc.); usual practice for seeking health care services (e.g., the nearest facility, distance of the nearest facility from home, the mode of transport to that facility, cost of transport to that facility, etc.); information on current/ present disease (e.g., current disease of the patient, duration of illness, whether the patient sought any treatment before or not, from where and whom they sought treatment, etc.); information about cost of treatment (e.g., direct medical cost, i.e., hospital charges, drug cost, diagnostic test, surgical procedure; direct non-medical cost, i.e., patient's additional food cost per day, attendants' additional food costs per day, attendants' residence cost per day, attendants' travel cost per day, informal cost/ tips; and indirect cost (income lost by both patient and attendant due to treatment.

Data collection instrument

The researchers conducted face to face interviews with a semi-structured questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire was prepared with the help of the Household Income and Expenditure Survey 2010 (HIES 2010). To conduct KII with the health managers, a structured checklist was used.

Method of Analysis

This study used univariate and bivariate methods in analyzing the data. In the univariate analysis, the background characteristics of the respondents were expressed in frequencies and percentages (%) and mean with standard deviation and presented in tabular format. In the bivariate analysis, the relationship of variables was analyzed in tabular format. To determine the significance of the difference in cost and outcome of health care in two different types of hospitals, t-test was used considering 5% level of significance. To analyze the effect of skill-mix and input-mix on the quality of care, a simple regression was conducted.

Regression analysis

To determine the effect of skill-mix and input-mix on the standard of care, a simple regression was conducted. The regression model employed in this study is as follows.

$$\text{Quality of care, measured by EuroQol-5D} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Age} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 \text{ Gender} + \beta_4 \text{ Currently facing any problem} + \beta_5 \text{ Skill-mix \& input-mix}$$

Here, quality of care, measured by EuroQol-5D is the multivariate dependent variable, and, the followings are independent variables, where,

Age= Age of each respondent

Education= Educational qualification of the respondent, a continuous variable which shows the highest class passed by the respondent

Gender= A dummy variable which indicated the sex of each patient and equals one if the patient is male and zero otherwise

Currently facing any problem= A dummy variable which indicates whether the patient faced any problems during the treatment process in this hospital

Skill-mix & input-mix= A dummy variable that shows whether the hospital had skill-mix and input-mix where the patient was admitted during the survey and it equals one for the treatment facilities and zero otherwise.

Another regression was run to analyze the effect of skill-mix and input-mix on the direct medical cost of the patients. The regression model is:

$$\text{Direct medical cost of the patients} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Age} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 \text{ Gender} + \beta_4 \text{ Currently facing any problem} + \beta_5 \text{ Skill-mix \& input-mix}$$

Here, direct medical cost of the patients is the multivariate dependent variable. The independent variables are as before.

Ethical consideration

The potential participants of the four health care facilities from two districts were informed verbally about the purpose of the study, type of information to be asked during the survey, as well as risks and benefits, confidentiality, and right to withdraw from the study. Before starting the interview, verbal consent was taken from the respondents. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary; and anonymity and privacy of the collected information were strictly maintained.

6. Results

Skill-mix of the hospitals

Medical professionals

The study found shortage of medical professionals of different posts, especially in the UHCs (Table 1).

From table 1, Baliakandi UHC was found to have the most severe health workforce vacancy among the four facilities with only 29% of the posts filled in of the total sanctioned posts, whereas about 53% were filled in Goalanda UHC. About half of the posts (49%) were filled in Rajbari DH and two-thirds (66%) of the posts were filled in Natore DH.

The UHCs had vacancies in some crucial posts like Junior Consultants, Anesthesiologist, and Radiologist. This implies that the UHCs could not perform any surgical procedure.

Overall, the treatment facilities had better skill-mix compared to the comparison facilities. The treatment facilities had emergency medical officers, pathologist, junior consultants of different specialties, and Homeo/Ayurvedic medical officer whereas the comparison facilities did not have any. In addition, Natore DH had the posts of Junior consultant of Medicine, Junior consultant of Anesthesia and Medical Officer (Paediatric) filled in. Thus, team building was easier in Natore DH and to some extent in Goalanda UHC that aided the facilities to produce better health services compared to the comparison facilities.

Table 1: Medical professionals in the facilities

Name of the positions of doctors	Treatment facilities				Comparison facilities			
	Natore District Hospital		Goalanda Upazila Health Complex		Rajbari District Hospital		Baliakandi Upazila Health Complex	
	Number of posts	Percentage of filled post	Number of posts	Percentage of filled post	Number of posts	Percentage of filled post	Number of posts	Percentage of filled post
Senior Consultant (Medicine)	-	-	-	-	1	100	-	-
Junior Consultant (Medicine)	1	100	1	0	1	0	1	0
Senior Consultant (Gynae & Obs.)	1	0	-	-	1	0	-	-
Junior Consultant (Gynae & Obs.)	-	-	1	100	1	100	1	0
Medical Officer (Gynae & Obs.)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Senior Consultant (Surgery)	1	100	-	-	1	100	-	-
Junior Consultant (Surgery)	-	-	1	0	1	0	1	0
Senior Consultant (Pediatrics)	1	0	-	-	1	100	-	-
Junior Consultant (Pediatrics)	-	-	1	100	1	0	1	0
Medical Officer (Pediatrics)	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Junior Consultant (Anesthesia)	1	100	1	0	1	0	1	0
Senior Consultant (Others)	3	33.33	-	-	6	50	-	-
Junior Consultant (Others)	2	50	5	40	6	33.33	-	-
Resident Medical Officer (RMO)	2	100	1	0	1	100	1	100
Medical Officer (MO)	9	100	8	50	4	75	2	100
Assistant Surgeon	-	-	-	-	11	18.18	-	-
Pathologist	1	100	1	100	1	0	-	-
Radiologist	2	50	-	-	1	100	-	-
Dental Surgeon	1	100	1	100	1	100	-	-
Emergency Medical Officer (EMO)	4	25	1	100	-	-	-	-
Anesthetist	2	0	1	0	-	-	-	-
Health Education Officer	1	0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Social Welfare Officer	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Homeo/Ayurvedic Medical Officer	1	100	1	100	1	0	-	-
Total	35	66.23	24	53.08	41	48.70	08	28.57

Support staff

It was found that Natore had 18% vacancy where Rajbari had 28% vacancy of support staff (Table 2). On the other hand, Goalanda had 33% vacancy and for Baliakandi the figure was 35%. There were also significant unfilled crucial posts like assistant nurse, cook, cleaner, ward boy in treatment facilities whereas this situation was more acute in comparison facilities which were under-resourced with crucial posts including staff nurses, ECG technician, OT assistant, ward boy, etc. Considering average filled posts, treatment facilities were more resourced with support staff compared to comparison facilities.

Table 2: Medical and non-medical support staff in the facilities

Name of the positions of staffs	Treatment facilities				Comparison facilities			
	Natore District Hospital		Goalanda Upazila Health Complex		Rajbari District Hospital		Baliakandi Upazila Health Complex	
	Number of posts sanctioned	Percentage of posts filled up	Number of posts sanctioned	Percentage of posts filled up	Number of posts sanctioned	Percentage of posts filled up	Number of posts sanctioned	Percentage of posts filled up
Medical assistant/SACMO	-	-	6	83.33	-	-	4	100
Matron/Nursing supervisor	2	100	1	100	2	50	-	-
Senior staff nurse	42	95.23	24	87.5	56	100	19	100
Staff nurse	15	100	-	-	11	100	-	-
Assistant nurse	5	25	-	-	5	60	1	100
OT assistant	-	-	1	100	1	0	-	-
Pharmacist	3	100	4	0	3	66.67	2	50
Lab technician	1	100	3	33.33	3	66.67	2	100
Technician X-ray	1	100	1	100	2	100	1	0
Technician (ECG)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Technician (U-sono)	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Technician (Other)	1	100	2	50	2	50	-	-
Ward boy: male/female	2	0	6	66.67	5	100	7	28.57
Receptionist	-	-	-	-	1	0	-	-
IT support stuff	1	100	-	-	2	100	-	-
Office assistant	-	-	9	55.55	5	100	-	-
Security guard	4	100	3	33.33	5	100	-	-
Cook	6	33.33	3	66.67	3	100	2	50
Driver	2	100	1	100	2	100	2	100
Cashier	2	100	1	100	1	0	1	100
Store keeper	1	100	1	0	1	100	1	0
Cleaner	22	68.18	5	80	8	100	2	50
Others	38	52.63	57	82.14	29	37.93	-	-
Total	149	81.91	128	66.97	147	71.56	44	64.88

Input-mix of the hospitals (surgical and diagnostic equipment)

From table 3, all of the facilities had anesthesia machine functional as sanctioned. Natore DH had 100% functional equipment as sanctioned to this facility and Goalanda UHC had 86% functional equipment. On the other hand, Rajbari DH and Baliakandi UHC had 74% and 64% functional sanctioned equipment respectively, implying that the comparison facilities had less functional input-mix compared to the treatment facilities. There was either a shortage of or no X-ray machine, diathermy, spectrophotometer and no functional ambulance in comparison facilities. None of the two ultrasonogram machine was functional in Rajbari DH. Of 20 sucker machines in Rajbari DH, 40% was found to be not functioning. Also, 33% of the colorimeters and 19% of the autoclave machines were found out of order in the same facility. Besides, there

was less or no functional desktop and laptop computers as well as printers in the comparison facilities. Both the Baliakandi UHC and Goalanda UHC had only 50% functional ECG machines.

Table 3: Level and status of medical equipment in the facilities

Category	Treatment facilities				Comparison facilities			
	Natore District Hospital		Goalanda Upazila Health Complex		Rajbari District Hospital		Baliakandi Upazila Health Complex	
	Available*	Functional %	Available*	Functional %	Available*	Functional %	Available*	Functional %
Ambulance	3	100	1	100	2	0	1	0
Anesthesia machine	4	100	1	100	5	100	1	100
Autoclave	7	100	2	100	11	81.81	2	100
C-arm	1	100	0	-	0	-	0	-
Colorimeter	1	100	0	-	3	66.67	0	-
Defibrillator	1	100	0	-	0	-	0	-
Desktop computer	38	100	3	100	39	84.62	3	66.67
Diathermy	6	100	0	-	5	40	0	-
ECG	3	100	2	50	3	100	2	50
Laparoscopy	1	100	0	-	1	100	0	-
Laptop computer	4	100	2	50	4	75	2	50
Laser printer	7	100	4	50	13	84.62	4	50
Microscope	4	100	2	100	7	85.71	2	100
Photocopy machine	2	100	1	100	1	100	0	-
Scanner	1	100	1	100	0	-	0	-
Slit lamp	1	100	0	-	0	-	0	-
Spectrophotometer	2	100	0	-	0	-	0	-
Sucker	21	100	15	80	20	60	9	55.56
Ultrasonogram	5	100	0	-	2	0	0	-
X-ray machine	3	100	1	100	5	80	0	-
Total	115	100	35	85.83	121	75.6	26	63.58

Note: *The term 'available' refers here the total number of equipment in all the surveyed facilities of each category

Quantitative Findings

Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Table 4 reports the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. The average age of the respondents was 44 years, of them, the highest portion (20%) belonged to the age group 41-50 years (the detailed age distribution is provided in the following table 5). Majority of the respondents (61%) were male. The mean year of schooling was 5 years. The majority had educational qualifications below Secondary School Certificate (SSC) and one-third of the respondents had no education (Table 6 in annex shows the detailed distribution of education). Moreover, there was a significant difference of 2.08 years in the education of respondents between treatment facilities and comparison facilities ($p < 0.0010$).

The majority of respondents (31.70%) were housewives followed by engagement in agriculture or fisheries (18.33%) and owner of small enterprise (14%). Most of the respondents (90%) are married. Average distance to the nearest healthcare facility, from which they seek care usually, from their own house is about 1.48 kilometer. Majority (35%) of the respondents have a monthly household income of below USD 117.65. About 57% of respondents' monthly income varies from USD 117.65 to USD 235.29.

Table 4: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Variable	Number of Observation	Mean/ Percentage	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Age	120	43.96	19.36	2	90
Gender	Male	73	60.83		
	Female	47	39.17		
Education (Highest Class Passed)	120	4.66	4.19	0	16
Occupation	Government service holder	3	2.50		
	Private job	9	7.50		
	Small enterprise	17	14.17		
	Medium enterprise	6	5.00		
	Agriculture/ Fisheries	22	18.33		
	Day laborer	15	12.50		
	Religious leader	1	0.83		
	Housewife	38	31.67		
	Retired	1	0.83		
	Immigrant	1	0.83		
Student	4	3.33			
Child/Elderly	3	2.50			
Marital Status	Married	108	90.00		
	Unmarried	12	10.00		
Monthly Household Income (USD)	≤ 117.65	42	35.00		
	117.66-235.29	68	56.67		
	235.30-352.94	5	4.17		
	352.95- 470.59	5	4.17		
Distance to facility from home (in kilometer)	120	1.48125	1.351222	.25	8

Note: 1 USD= BDT 85

Table 5: Age distribution of the respondents

Age group	Frequency	Percentage
01-10	1	0.83
11-20	17	14.17
21-30	20	16.67
31-40	18	15.00
41-50	24	20.00
51-60	19	15.83
Above 60	21	17.50
Total	120	100

Usual practice for seeking health care services

More than one-fourth of the respondents (27%) mentioned about d pharmacy/dispensary as the nearest facility to their houses, while 22% mentioned about Upazila Health Complex. Only 15.83% of the respondents had District Hospital/General Hospital as the nearest facility (Table 7 in annex).

A larger portion (74%) of the respondents used an auto-rickshaw to reach to the nearest health care facility for seeking care, followed by rickshaw (14%), rickshaw van (10%). Most of them (53%) were accompanied by the spouse to access that facility, followed by parents (21%) and children (20%).

Information on current/present disease

Majority of the patients (n=28, 23.33%) respondents got themselves admitted due to injury and/or disability. Twenty (17%) had asthma/breathing problems, and ten (8.33%) had heart disease as the cause of admission to the hospital, detailed disease pattern is shown in table 8 in annex. All of the respondents (120) had one attendant who stayed with him/her throughout the whole day. The attendant was staying at the hospital premises with their patients at night.

Eighty-three percent of respondents mentioned suffering from less than one month for the disease or health problems they got admitted themselves for, followed by 6 months- 1 year (8%). The rest had been suffering either for 1-3 months, or 3-6 months, or more than one year (Table 9 in annex). Of 120 respondents, 34 (29%) sought treatment before and the rest 71% did not seek any treatment before getting admitted into the respective hospitals. Almost half of the respondents (47%) sought treatment from private health facilities and 21% went to public facilities earlier. The rest 32% sought care from pharmacy/dispensaries (Table 10 in annex). Majority (68%) of the respondents received treatment from a qualified physician, the rest

received care either from an unqualified/informal provider including a salesman of a pharmacy/dispensary (26%) or an ayurved/kabiraj/hekim (6%).

Out of 120 respondents, 58 (48%) stated that they were facing problems/obstacles during the hospital stay and the rest 62 faced no problems. Of the 58 reported to face problems, 16 (28%) respondents mentioned the lack of diagnostic facilities in the hospital. 14 (24%) reported the issue of shortage of doctors and nurses (Table 11 in annex).

Cost and quality of care of the patients

Cost and EuroQol-5D scores of the patients

Table 12 summarizes the total cost and EuroQol-5D scores. The average total cost of all the respondents was, around USD 59.69 (\pm 38.29) where the minimum cost was USD 10.85 and the maximum was USD 226.73. This is to be noted that public facilities do not charge any bed charge for hospital stay and fee for conducting surgery. The average direct medical cost was USD 20.59(\pm 26.05), direct non-medical cost is USD 2 (\pm 1.53), and indirect cost of the patient is a bit higher (USD 37.07 \pm 28.21) than the earlier two components.

Table 12: Average cost and EuroQol-5D scores of the respondents

Item	Observation	Mean/ Percentage	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Total cost (USD)	120	59.69	38.29	10.85	226.73
Direct medical cost (USD)	120	20.59	26.05	0.06	198.88
Direct non-medical cost (USD)	120	2.02	1.53	0.18	11.76
Indirect cost (USD)	120	37.07	28.21	5.01	208.62
EuroQol-5D score	120	0.32	0.38	-0.59	0.85
Mobility	No problem	37	30.83		
	Some problem	64	53.33		
	Extreme problem	19	15.83		
Self-care	No problem	32	26.67		
	Some problem	69	57.50		
	Extreme problem	19	15.83		
Usual activities	No problem	17	14.17		
	Some problem	72	74.17		
	Extreme problem	31	25.83		
Pain/ discomfort	No problem	13	10.83		
	Some problem	87	72.50		
	Extreme problem	20	16.67		
Anxiety/ depression	No problem	11	9.17		
	Some problem	82	68.33		
	Extreme problem	27	22.50		

Note: 1 USD= BDT 85

Average EuroQol-5D score of all the respondents was 0.32 (SD: 0.39; range: -0.60 to 0.85). Among the components/indicators of EuroQol-5D, 31% of patients reported having no problem with their mobility whereas 53% had slight and 16% had an extreme problem with mobility. Twenty-seven percent of patients could perform self-care but 58% had slight problem and 16% could not perform without the help of someone else. About 14% of patients were involved in usual activities without any trouble, 74% had some sort of problem and 26% had extreme problems regarding involvement in usual activities. Eleven percent of patients do not feel any pain/discomfort whereas 73% had some sort of pain and 17% had extreme pain/discomfort. Only 9% of the patients have no anxiety/depression whereas 68% had some sort of anxiety and the rest (23%) had extreme anxiety during the survey.

Comparison of cost between treatment and comparison facilities

This part compares cost incurred by the patients from treatment facilities and comparison facilities. Table 13 reports the summary of cost.

Table 13: Comparison of cost between treatment and comparison facilities

Item	Treatment facilities		Comparison facilities		Difference	
	Observation	Mean	Observation	Mean	Diff= [mean (comparison)-mean (treatment)]	Pr.
Total cost (USD)	60	52.26	60	67.12	14.86**	0.016
Direct medical cost (USD)	60	13.39	60	27.80	14.41***	0.001
Direct non-medical cost (USD)	60	1.95	60	2.10	0.15	0.291
Indirect cost (USD)	60	36.92	60	37.22	0.30	0.477

Note: ***,** and * represents significance at 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively
1 USD= BDT 85

The respondents from comparison facilities incurred significantly ($p < 0.016$) higher cost of USD 14.86 than those from treatment facilities. Direct medical cost of the patients was, on average, USD 13.39 in treatment facilities whereas it was USD 27.80 for comparison facilities. This difference was also significant ($p < 0.001$). As direct non-medical cost and indirect cost and these were almost similar in each facility, no significant difference was found there.

Comparison of EuroQol-5D scores between treatment and comparison facilities

Table 14 shows that the average score of EuroQol-5D was 0.49 in the treatment facilities, while in the comparison facilities, the average score was 0.15. This is to be noted that the larger the EuroQol-5D score, the better the quality of care the patient received.

Table 14: EuroQol-5D scores in treatment and comparison facilities

Item	Treatment facilities		Comparison facilities		Difference	
	Observation	Mean	Observation	Mean	Diff= [mean (comparison)-mean (treatment)]	Pr.
EuroQol-5D score	60	0.49	60	0.15	0.34***	0.000
Mobility	60	1.65 [†]	60	2.05 [†]	0.4***	0.001
Self-care	60	1.63 [†]	60	2.15 [†]	0.52***	0.000
Usual activities	60	1.83 [†]	60	2.42 [†]	0.6***	0.000
Pain/discomfort	60	1.98 [†]	60	2.13 [†]	0.15	0.117
Anxiety/depression	60	1.97 [†]	60	2.3 [†]	0.33***	0.001

Notes: ***, ** and * represents significance at 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.

[†] The smaller the value, the better the quality of health care the patient received

The score of EuroQol-5D in treatment facilities was significantly higher than that of comparison facilities (p=0.000).

Again, the score of mobility, self-care, usual activities, and anxiety/depression was significantly (p≤0.001) higher in comparison facilities than that of treatment facilities. As the EuroQol-5D score was higher in treatment facilities, it can be said that the quality of care was better in the treatment facilities than comparison facilities. These findings are visualized in the following figure 2.

Figure 2: Difference in EuroQol-5D score due to skill-mix and input-mix

Results from Regression Analysis

Regression results are represented in table 15. It was found that the skill-mix and input-mix of the hospital had a significant ($p = 0.000$) effect on the perceived healthiness of the patient. If the hospital had skill-mix and input-mix, score of EuroQol-5D of the patients significantly increased by 0.27. Education and age also had significant effects on the EuroQol-5D score. If education increased by one year, the EuroQol-5D score of the patient increased by 0.02 ($p=0.016$). On the contrary, if age increased by one year, the EuroQol-5D score decreased by 0.003 ($p=0.09$).

Table 15: Effect of skill-mix and input-mix on the quality of care

EuroQol-5D score	Coefficient	Standard Error	p-value
Age	-0.003*	0.002	0.090
Education	0.019**	0.008	0.016
Gender	0.012	0.066	0.871
Currently facing any problem	0.055	0.068	0.419
Skill-mix & input-mix	0.268***	0.070	0.000
Constant	0.120	0.182	0.511
R-squared = 0.2730		Number of observation = 120	
Adj R-squared = 0.2412		F(5, 114) = 8.56	
		Prob > F = 0.0000	

Note: ***, ** and * represents 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance, respectively.

As it is seen earlier that the two types of health facilities had a significant cost difference in direct medical cost incurred by the patients, a simple regression was run to find the effect of skill-mix and input-mix on the direct medical cost of the patients (results shown in table 16).

Table 16: Effect of skill-mix and input-mix on the direct medical cost of the patients

Direct medical cost	Coefficient	Standard Error	p-value
Age	0.25**	0.12	0.047
Education	0.08	0.59	0.889
Gender	7.81	4.91	0.114
Currently facing any problem	-5.70	5.05	0.261
Skill-mix & input-mix	-12.72**	5.19	0.016
Constant	13.34	13.52	0.326
R-squared = 0.1336		Number of observation = 120	
Adj R-squared = 0.0956		F(5, 114) = 3.51	
		Prob > F = 0.0054	

Note: ***, ** and * represents 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance, respectively.

It is seen from table that if the hospital had skill-mix and input-mix, direct medical cost of the patients significantly ($p=0.016$) decreased by USD 12.72. Age was also found to be significantly ($p=0.047$) associated with direct medical cost. If age increased by 1 year, direct medical cost of the patient significantly increased by USD 0.25.

Findings from the qualitative survey

Four key informant interviews (KIIs) were conducted with the health managers from the four health care facilities i.e. two superintendents from the two DH and one UHFPO and one RMO from the UHCs. The key informants were working in the facility from 4 months to 4.5 years. They were asked about availability/ shortage of skill-mix, input-mix, the effect of the shortage of skill-mix and input-mix on quality of care, and their suggestions to improve skill-mix and input-mix of the hospital.

The health manager from a treatment facility reported of having adequate medical professionals and also mentioned of having 80% consultants and 67% nurses staffed. Health manager from another treatment facility reported having adequate nurses but a shortage of doctors and other support staff. Managers of comparison facilities reported about an extreme shortage of doctors. One respondent revealed that only one-third (17 out of 42) of the doctors were available in his facility. He specified that,

“After 2.30 pm, only one doctor serves the whole hospital. Even in case of emergency or casualty, usually, there is no additional staff available after duty hours (2:30 pm), thus one RMO has to treat the emergency cases as well as the patients in the in-patient department (IPD), which makes impossible to maintain the proper quality of care provided. Besides, we lack the digital X-ray machine’s functionality and the human resource required to operate ultrasonography and laparoscopy machines as well as a dental unit there (40 years old, male, postgraduate, 6 months of experience).”

While having adequate bulk of nurses, the respondent also felt the importance of the post of “Assistant Senior Nurses” to deliver health care at inpatient services. Respondent from another comparison facility mentioned that along with the shortage of doctors, the facility lacked support staff. The main reasons behind the shortage of medical professionals, stated by them, from their perspective, included lack of adequate facilities (e.g., house rent, transport facility, etc.), incentive and other benefits for providing services in facilities situated other than large cities; canceling of posting in these hospitals through political influences; and lack of post creation in response to the need of the people. The health managers agreed that the shortage of medical and support staff hinders the quality of care provided by the respective hospitals. It

supports findings from document review that the treatment facilities had adequate medical professionals than the comparison facilities.

The health managers were asked about the adequacy of equipment available (input-mix) required for hospital operation. One of the health managers stated to have all equipment and inputs to provide health care whereas the others mentioned having a shortage of input-mix which affected hospital provided quality of care. Though supplies of drugs were adequate in these hospitals, due to lack of functioning machinery (e.g., ultra-sonogram machine) and manpower (e.g., sonologist) to operate them in the comparison facilities, patients needed to get X-ray and ultrasonography done from outside. In fact, one of the treatment facilities also lacked X-ray machine, so the radiographical services could not be provided. Lengthiness of repairing the equipment once they are dysfunctional is the only reason for shortage/lack of inputs, stated by the health managers. A respondent from a treatment facility stated that,

“Our health complex has all facilities except the X-ray machine which has not been working for long. We send a letter to corresponding authority in Dhaka; people from National Electro- Medical Equipment Maintenance Workshop (NEMEMW) unit visit the hospital to investigate non-functional/repairable machine(s); recommend to repair the machine(s), and then the machine(s) are repaired. It takes a lot of time to repair the machine(s), sometimes it has been too late to repair a machine/equipment (40 years old, male, postgraduate, 6 months of experience).”

Manager of a treatment facility mentioned regarding inputs available to his facility,

“We have adequate inputs according to the demand and needs of the patients here. Currently, we have lesser than required posts for cleaners and so the cleaners are outsourced where the fund for this purpose is managed by raising funds locally.” (50 years old, male, postgraduate, 1.5 years of experience)

Major suggestions from the health managers include: to improve skill-mix in the hospital included appointing more human resources, with a special focus on medical professional (e.g., consultant, EMO, RMO, etc.) as well as other support staff (e.g., paramedics, lab technician, cleaners, etc.); ensuring basic amenities and other benefits to keep doctors retained in district or upazila level and provide incentives for that, and extending the duration of mandatory service of newly appointed doctors at upazila level from 2 years to 5 years. Suggestions for improving input-mix included introducing an easy process to repair or install a machine/equipment; coordination of functional machines and manpower; maintaining surveillance and reporting system; providing autonomy to the hospital manager to some extent to manage repairing/ outsourcing support staff, etc. locally. Besides, to improve the quality of care through

improving input-mix, IT instruments and supply of the internet needed to be ensured as well as generator/IPS/solar system for backing up during load shedding/power cut and security camera was needed to prevent things to be stolen.

7. Discussion

This study tried to find out the effect of skill-mix and input-mix on the cost incurred by the patients and the quality of care measured by EuroQol-5D. Total cost of the respondents was, on average, around USD 59.69 and average of direct medical cost was USD 20. The cost of treatment could be reduced if adequate diagnostic facilities in the hospitals was ensured as diagnostic tests cost less in public facilities compared to the private ones. While comparing the cost incurred by the patients in two different types of hospitals, average total cost in treatment facilities was USD 52.26 whereas it was USD 67.12 for comparison facilities. Respondents from facilities with lower input-mix and skill-mix incurred about USD 14.86 more than the treatment facilities ($p < 0.05$), which indicates that the shortages of skill-mix and input-mix lead to increased cost of treatment. The findings are consistent with other relevant studies by Dixon, Kaambwa, Nancarrow, Martin, & Bryan (2010); and Thungjaroenkul, Cummings, & Embleton (2007).

The average score of EuroQol-5D was 0.317 for all the respondents. Separately, the score was 0.486 in the treatment facilities and 0.148 in the comparison facilities. Two types of hospitals had a significant ($p = 0.000$) difference in the score of EuroQol-5D. This is to note that the larger the score, the better the standard of hospital provided health care. This finding demonstrates that proper skill-mix and input-mix result in a significant effect on the quality of care through improving the health status of the patients, as suggests by Dixon, Kaambwa, Nancarrow, Martin, & Bryan (2010); Kim, Harrington, & Greene (2009); Bourgeault, Kuhlmann, E., & Wrede (2008); Aiken et al. (2017), Thungjaroenkul, Cummings, & Embleton (2007); and Freund, et al. (2015).

Regression analysis showed that the availability of skill-mix and input-mix in the hospital significantly ($p = 0.000$) increased the EuroQol-5D value of the patients by 0.27. This confirms the initial hypothesis of this paper that skill-mix and input-mix have a positive effect on the perceived quality of hospital care. One-year increase in education resulted in a higher score of EuroQol-5D, this may be due to the reason that more educated persons can understand the prescriptions and the advice of the doctors and can comply more with these compared to less

educated persons. By increasing literacy, the outcome of health care (perceived quality of care) could be improved. Again, it was found that if the hospital has higher skill-mix and input-mix, direct medical cost significantly ($p < 0.016$) reduced by USD 12.72. This finding is consistent with the study results by Thungjaroenkul, Cummings, & Embleton (2007); Bourgeault, Kuhlmann, E., & Wrede (2008); and Dixon, Kaambwa, Nancarrow, Martin, & Bryan (2010).

From the qualitative findings, it was found that the situation is better in the treatment facilities compared to the comparison facilities. This finding has policy implications, in terms of the government's initiative to ensure the provision of quality health care at the district or below level. This calls for need-based allocation both in budgetary and human resource allocation.

The study tried to discuss the main reasons for worse skill-mix and input-mix in this subsection, based on the quantitative findings from surveys and qualitative findings from KIIs with health managers. It was found that proper skill-mix and input-mix results in improved quality of care and reduced cost incurred by the patients.

Limitation of the study

Due to resource constraints, only 120 respondents could be interviewed. With such a small sample size, influences of skill-mix and input-mix cannot be determined accurately, and so we cannot generalize the findings. Data were collected from two secondary level hospitals and two primary level hospitals as mentioned above. Findings may encounter if data include other secondary and primary level health care facilities also.

8. Recommendations and Conclusion

Some recommendations may be helpful in policy formation to enhance the standard of care provided in the district and upazila level and reduce cost of treatment borne by the patients.

- **Task shifting**

Enhancing the standard of care provided in public health care facilities, especially in the district or upazila level, increasing the number of doctors, nurses and other supportive medical staff (e.g., paramedics, technicians, etc.) is a must. The government should have a long-term plan with a focus on increasing human resources to cope up with the increased demand for health care. But, for the short term or medium term, task shifting can be an intermediate solution. Nurses and paramedics can be allowed to work with specialized and expert doctors for as long as possible time to acquire knowledge and skills which can be applied later in the absence of

the expert, where possible and permissible. This may enhance the quality of care of public hospitals.

- **Establishing nursing and others (e.g., technician, paramedics, etc.) profession as rewarding ones**

In current practice, professions including nursing, technician, paramedics, etc. are not seen as decent ones in our society. Moreover, salary and other benefits are not so attractive and so these professions cannot attract the meritorious students to join. To attract the students in these professions, making these worthwhile is recommended. This can be made possible by setting up a uniform, well-paid salary structure for these professions to be abiding by all the public and private hospitals as well as forming societal respect and awareness about them.

- **Ensuring enough functional medical equipment in primary level facility**

To ensure quality health care, especially at district and upazila level, health care facilities need functional medical equipment such as diagnostic equipment, uninterrupted supply of electricity, water, and other medical gases, etc. Again, the existing dysfunctional equipment must be repaired instantly and made functional and the new equipment should be installed.

- **Introducing institutional practice and providing some autonomy for maintaining equipment**

Through introducing institutional practices in the evening by the doctors, hospitals can generate revenue, a portion of which may be deposited to government treasury and the other portion may be regulated and spent by the hospital manager for the betterment of the hospital including outsourcing support staff, repairing equipment, infrastructural development, etc. However, transparency must be maintained during this process and strict monitoring should be ensured.

- **Introducing one stop services in hospitals at district or below level**

One of the potential factors contributing to higher cost of treatment is lack of medical professionals as well as all proper diagnostic facilities in the hospitals. As a result, patients may go outside of the public hospitals, especially to the private commercial hospitals/clinic; seek treatment and conduct tests there; and bear a higher health expenditure. If required medical professionals and all the diagnostic facilities are available in one public hospital, patients need not go outside. This calls for setting up one-stop services in hospitals at district or below level.

Conclusion

This study assessed the effect of skill-mix and input-mix on cost and outcome of the hospital care, where the outcome was measured by EuroQol-5D. The study was conducted in four public hospitals, where two public hospitals had better performance in terms of skill-mix and input-mix (termed as treatment facilities) than the other two different hospitals (termed as comparison facilities). It was found that cost are significantly lower in treatment facilities compared to comparison facilities. The study also found that the perceived health status of the patients is significantly better and so EuroQol-5D score is higher in treatment facilities than that of comparison facilities. This confirms that better skill-mix and input-mix results in reduced cost of health care and improved quality of care provided in the public hospitals.

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Dedication

1. Conceptualization: Fariha Kadir
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3. Writing – review, editing, drafting and finalizing: Fariha Kadir and Aninda Nishat Moitry

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest in the research reported in this paper.

Annex

Table 6: Distribution of education among respondents

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
No Education	41	34.17
Below Secondary School Certificate (SSC)	57	47.50
Secondary School Certificate (SSC)	16	13.33
Higher Secondary Certificate (HSC)	5	4.17
Graduate	1	0.83
Total	120	100

Table 7: Nearest healthcare facility of the respondents

Nearest healthcare facility	Frequency	Percentage
Satellite Clinic	2	1.67
Community Clinic	19	15.83
Union Health & Family Welfare Center/ Union Sub Center/ Rural Health Center	14	11.67
Upazila Health Complex	26	21.67
District Hospital/ General Hospital	19	15.83
Private health facility	8	6.67
Pharmacy/dispensary	32	26.67
Total	120	100

Table 8: Disease profile of the respondents

Name of the Disease	Frequency	Percentage
Chronic Fever	3	2.5
Injuries / Disability	28	23.33
Asthma/ Breathing problem	20	16.67
Chronic Dysentery	1	0.83
Gastric/ ulcer	4	3.33
Piles	4	3.33
Paralysis	3	2.5
Epilepsy	1	0.83
Diarrhea	1	0.83
Fever	1	0.83
Dysentery	3	2.5
Pain	5	4.17
Stroke	1	0.83
Gall stone Diseases	1	0.83
Hypertension	3	2.5
Heart disease	10	8.33
Skin disease	5	4.17
Anemia	9	7.5
Hernia	1	0.83
Weakness	9	7.5
Kidney Diseases	1	0.83
Tumor	6	5
Total	120	100

Table 9: Duration of illness from disease of the respondents

Healthcare facility	Frequency	Percentage
<1 month	100	83.33
1-3 Months	4	3.33
3-6 months	3	2.50
6 months- 1 year	9	7.50
>1 year	4	3.33
Total	120	100

Table 10: Place of receiving health care before admitting to current facility

Healthcare facility	Frequency	Percentage
Upazila Health Complex	2	5.88
District Hospital/ General Hospital	5	14.71
Private health facility	16	47.06
Pharmacy/dispensary	11	32.35
Total	34	100

Table 11: Problems faced by the respondents during treatment process

Reason for problems	Frequency	Percentage
Treatment cost is too much	2	3.45
Misbehave of doctor(s)	1	1.72
Misbehave of nurse(s)	4	6.9
Residence of attendants	5	8.62
Food accommodation of attendants	1	1.72
Smaller number of doctor-nurse	14	24.14
Late response of nurses	5	8.62
Lack of diagnostic test facilities	16	27.59
Lack of adequate cleanliness	10	17.24
Total	58	100

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